

Proposal for a point comparison of apparent positions etc

L Lindegren 1987 Nov 13 (ver. 1)

The purpose of this comparison is to check our understanding of the most important quantities involved in the computation of the apparent position of the star, the position of its image in the field of view and on the main grid. Originally, only a comparison of apparent positions was envisaged, but I believe it would be worth while to carry this exercise all the way through to the modulation phase on the main grid. The comparison would then encompass the following major transformations:

1. from astrometric parameters to the geometric position;
2. from geometric to apparent position, including the use of geocentric orbit data;
3. from celestial direction to field coordinates, including attitude data;
4. from field coordinates to a grid coordinate, including medium-scale grid errors.

Using well-defined intermediate quantities as check-points makes it possible to follow only part of the chain, or to locate more easily the origin of any differences.

This note is intended to give a complete listing of all items needed as input to the calculations, of suitable check-points, and of the known relations between FAST and NDAC quantities in cases where they do not coincide. Numerical values are not given, but I am prepared to supply the full set of input, intermediate and output data if there is sufficient interest in this exercise.

1. Calculation of geometric position (coordinate direction)

<i>Input:</i>	t_{ref}	= reference epoch
	t_{obs}	= epoch of observation
	α	= Right Ascension at t_{ref}
	δ	= Declination at t_{ref}
	$\mu_{\alpha} \cos \delta$	= proper motion in R.A.
	μ_{δ}	= proper motion in Dec.
	π	= parallax
	v_r	= radial velocity
<i>Output:</i>	α_{geo}	= geocentric geometric R.A.
	δ_{geo}	= geocentric geometric Dec.
	r_{be}	= barycentric position of the Earth at t_{ref} t_{obs}

NOTES: t_{ref} may correspond to J1990.0. t_{obs} is the time of light reception at the satellite, *not* ground-station time. Both times are on a scale uniformly related to TAI. All positions and proper motions are referred to the mean equinox and equator of J2000.0. The geometric position includes proper motion (also perspective effects) and the annual parallax, but not diurnal parallax, light deflection or aberration. An Earth ephemeris is assumed to be available.

2. Calculation of apparent position (proper direction)

<i>Input:</i>	TBEGIN, TEND, TREF, STATE(6), AUXKEP(5), SCALE, CHEBY(10,6)	= geocentric orbit data on DDID format
	CATAI	= number of seconds that must be added to UTC to obtain TAI
	$\lambda_g \ \varphi_g \ h_g$	= geodetic longitude, latitude and altitude of the ground station
<i>Output:</i>	α_{app}	= satellitocentric apparent R.A.
	δ_{app}	= satellitocentric apparent Dec.
	r_{gh}	= geocentric position of the satellite at $t_{ref} - \tau$
	r_{bh}	= barycentric position of the satellite at $t_{ref} - \tau$
	v_{gh}	= geocentric velocity of the satellite at $t_{ref} - \tau$
	v_{bh}	= barycentric velocity of the satellite at $t_{ref} - \tau$
	r_{bs}	= barycentric position of the Sun at $t_{ref} - \tau$
	τ	= spacecraft-to-ground propagation delay

NOTES: The apparent position includes light deflection by the Sun and Earth, and aberration corresponding to the barycentric velocity of the satellite. Diurnal parallax may or may not be included. The ground station time corresponding to the observation is $t_{obs} + \tau$.

3. Calculation of field coordinates

<i>Input:</i>	$\bar{v}_0 \ \Omega_0$	= initial angles for the NSL
	γ	= basic angle
<i>Output:</i>	p or f	= preceding or following field
	x y (w z)	= field coordinates
	I J	= scanfield indices ($1 \leq I \leq 168, 1 \leq J \leq 46$)

NOTES: The true attitude is assumed to coincide with the NSL (TBR). The nominal relation between the field coordinates as defined by FAST (x, y) and NDAC (w, z) is

$$w = -\cos y \sin x$$

$$z = +\sin y$$

4. Calculation of the grid coordinate and modulation phase

Input: a_{ij} = field-to-grid transformation coefficients ($i + j \leq 3$)
 $MSI(i,j)$ = medium scale irregularities ($1 \leq i \leq 168, 1 \leq j \leq 46$)

Output: G = grid coordinate of the stellar image on the main grid
 ϕ = modulation phase of the IDT signal

NOTES: For the transformation $(x, y) \rightarrow G_{\text{FAST}}$ see Mignard, Falin & Froeschle (1986), while for the transformation $(w, z) \rightarrow G_{\text{NDAC}}$ see NDAC/LO/084.1 (with g_{ij} replacing a_{ij}). The modulation phase ϕ is defined by the standard expression for the light modulation,

$$I = I_0 [1 + M_1 \cos \phi + M_2 \cos 2\phi]$$

MSI is included in ϕ but not in G .